

Original Article

CHALLENGES TO INTEGRATION OF TREASURY SINGLE ACCOUNT (TSA) INTO THE ACCOUNTING EDUCATION CURRICULUM OF COLLEGES OF EDUCATION

¹Ogbonnaya Okorie Ph.D and ²Felicia Ogonna Nwokike P.h.D, MABEN¹Ebonyi State College of Education, Ikwo, Nigeria.²Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology. Enugu, Nigeria.Email: Ogbonnayaokorie15@yahoo.com
ogonnanwokike@yahoo.comDOI: <https://doi.org/>

10.5281/zenodo.17435165

Abstract

This study examined challenges to integration of treasury single account (TSA) into the Accounting Education curriculum of Colleges of Education. Integration of TSA will make Accounting Education curriculum an anti-corruption curriculum that will, in turn, lead to the production of credible accountants especially in a public-sector-driven economy like Nigeria. The study identified poor knowledge of subject matter, poor funding, inconsistency in public policies, poor response to changes in economic and financial policies, resistance to change, slavish attachment to existing curriculum and absence of training for Accounting Education lecturers as the major challenges to the integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum of Colleges of Education. The study also identified the strategies for enhancing integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum to include re-training of Accounting Education lecturers, provision of adequate funds and professionalizing Accounting Education. The researchers recommended (inter alia) that Accounting Education lecturers should have a strong professional body that would be organizing mandatory professional development programmes for members, while government should involve them in making critical economic and financial policies that concern Accounting Education.

Keywords: *Integration, Treasury Single Account, Accounting Education Curriculum*

Introduction

Out of the three major types of institutions meant to provide Tertiary Education in Nigeria, Colleges of Education are set aside to train teachers to handle Basic Education. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2013) affirmed that Colleges of Education produce graduates with the Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) which is the minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession. On this premise, Eneja

and Akamigbo (2020) described Colleges of Education as a Tertiary Education institution authorized to offer teacher education programme and produce competent teachers issued with the minimum teaching qualification (NCE) to teach at the Basic Education level. Eneja and Akamigbo explained that Basic Education comprised pre-primary education, primary education, adult and non-formal education, special needs education and

junior secondary education. This global scope and the eclectic nature of Colleges of Education demands the offering of many and varied courses such as Accounting Education.

In line with the above, Accounting Education is one of the courses offered in Colleges of Education. Accounting Education is offered either as a course or an area of specialization in Business Education. At the NCE level, Accounting Education aims at equipping recipients with the right type of skills that will enable them enter into personal business, work in offices or teach business subjects (Accounting inclusive). Accounting Education programme in Colleges of Education makes students accessible to Accounting Education curriculum which Duru (2016) referred to as systematized experiences and programmes that learners must pass through for their certification and award of honour. In order to produce competent Accounting Education graduates in Colleges of Education, curriculum integration approach should be adopted for effective organization of both contents and experiences.

However, integration refers to the process or action of successfully joining or combining two or more things. It can, as well, be described as the adoption of an element or an idea into an area to which it does not naturally or originally belong. Applying this construct to curriculum organization, Obih (2018) described curriculum integration as the application of curricular elements from one field of study in other fields of study so that they buttress and reinforce one another. Obih believed that curriculum integration is an effective curriculum arrangement standard which holds that, learning experiences and subject matter should be accurately organized in a unified and up-to-date manner. Finally, Obih pointed out that curriculum contents should be formulated in harmony with new concepts, principles, theories and new ways of solving problems. In tune with the

foregoing, Alwi in Rashed and Tamuri (2020) opined that every curriculum organization should take the challenge of balancing the current needs of the society. Rashed and Tamuri further explained that the concept of knowledge should be developed broadly and applied integratively based on the current reality rather than being static in a segregated manner. In the same vein, taking an evaluative approach, Wall and Leckie (2017) opined that curriculum integration can lead to an attractive, resolute, applicable and useful approach to teaching and learning. Again, Wall and Leckie explained that curriculum integration involves purposeful learning planned to cover issues that are important to teachers and learners. Summarily, a critical financial policy like Treasury Single Account (TSA) should be integrated into the Accounting Education curriculum. TSA is an arrangement in public accounting that mandates that every revenue, receipts and income should be pooled into a single account while every payment is made from the same account. Udo (2016) applauded this view by describing TSA as a public account arrangement whereby the government uses a single account or a set of unified accounts to ensure that every receipt and payment is made through a Consolidated Revenue Account (CRA) domiciled at the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). Udo further explained that:

- All Ministries, Departments and Agencies (MDAs) remit their revenues to the Consolidated Revenue Account (CRA) through Deposit Money Banks (DMBs) on a fee-for-service basis.
- All monies collected must be remitted to the CRA at the end of every banking day so that every MDA account must be returned to zero balance at the end of every banking day.
- TSA account types include main account, subsidiary account, transaction account, zero balance account, imprest account, transit account and

correspondence account for different transaction purposes. Treasury Single Account (TSA) was introduced by the Federal Republic of Nigeria to ensure judicious use of all government monies. Odewale (2016) described TSA as a financial policy which the Federal Republic of Nigeria introduced in 2012 in order to consolidate all receipts from MDAs through depositing into commercial banks connected to the single account at the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN). Succinctly put, TSA is a major change in the economic and financial system of Nigeria. It is an arrangement, according to Mba (2016), in public accounting in which all government revenue, receipts and income are pooled into a single account usually domiciled in the CBN while all payments are made from there. In the same manner Pattanayak and Fainboin in Udo and Esara (2016) opined that TSA is a bank account or a group of unified bank accounts through which a government does all receipts and payments, and determines its consolidated cash position on daily basis. In consonance with the above, Oyeleke in Udo and Esara (2016) described TSA as the amalgamation of all government bank accounts so that the government will have a consolidated overview of its cash resources. The CBN (2016) summarily described TSA as the concept of consolidating government bank accounts in a single account or a set of affiliated accounts for all government payments and receipts. The CBN explained that the first of the two models of TSA is where the Main TSA and associated ledger sub-accounts (where they exist) are maintained in a single banking institution, whereas the second model is where the Main TSA is maintained in one banking institution while affiliated zero balance ledger sub-accounts (where they exist) are kept in other banking institutions. SystemSpecs, Interswich, Unified Payment Services, e-Transact, Nigeria Inter-Bank Settlement System (NIBSS),

Paystack, Remita and Flutterwave were listed by the CBN as licensed payment platforms. Treasury Single Account is and should be a familiar idea in Nigeria. It marks a giant stride towards the implementation of the provisions of sections 80 (1) and 120 (1) of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (as amended). These sections provide that “all revenues or other moneys raised or received by the Federation/State (not being revenue or other moneys payable under this Constitution or any Act/Law of the National/House of Assembly into any other public fund of the Federation/State established for a specific purpose) shall be paid into and form one consolidated revenue fund of the Federation/State”. This provision was abandoned until 2012 when the Federal Government decided to test run it with two hundred and seventeen (217) Ministries, Departments and Agencies. Confirming the test run, Udo and Esara (2016) posited that the pilot TSA began in 2012 with 217 MDAs using Consolidated Systematic Accounting for accountability and transparency in public fund management. Udo and Esara further explained that the result of the pilot TSA revealed that the scheme saved about five hundred billion naira (₦500 billion) that would have gone into frivolous spending for Nigeria. Oyedele in Udo and Esara held that it was the success of the pilot scheme that made the Federal Republic of Nigeria to direct every deposit money bank (DMB) to create the technology platform to accommodate all MDAs in the TSA stratagem. In agreement with the above assertion, Odewale (2016) held that it was the result of the TSA pilot scheme that made Muhammadu Buhari (the then President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria) to give an executive order directing all DMBs to implement the Remita e-collection which translated to collection and remittance of all government revenues to a consolidated account domiciled with the CBN. That

proclamation evidenced the formal adoption of TSA by the Federal Republic of Nigeria and signalled a critical economic and financial change in the country.

Treasury Single Account (TSA): Its Implications for Accounting Education Curriculum

Being a critical change in the economic and financial policy of the country, TSA has some implications for the Accounting Education Curriculum. One of these implications, according to Arinze and Chukwuka (2018), is knowledge explosion and change in educational objectives (arising from change in societal values) as reasons for selection of curriculum contents. This position supports Offorma (2016) that societal aims, meanings, norms and values are critical elements to consider while determining curriculum contents. Standing on this premise, Maali and Ali-Attar (2020) opined that Accounting Education curriculum shall be responsive to changes and innovations in the economic and financial policies of a country since Accounting is the language and soul of business. TSA can, no doubt, be described as an innovation in the economic and financial policies of Nigeria.

As an innovation, TSA is expected to consolidate the position of Accounting Education graduates. Integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum should strengthen students both in character and learning. White in Ocheni (2016) affirming this position observed that TSA would introduce economy and efficiency into the financial management of the country. Similarly, Larson in Ocheni posited that TSA ought to enhance transparency and accountability in public financial management. Integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum would translate the curriculum into an anti-corruption curriculum which Awajiokinor and Binta (2020) described as the only sure way to nab corruption in Nigeria. No

doubt, Accounting Education curriculum is one of the areas into which anti-corruption values can be carefully integrated to enable it participate in war against corruption in Nigeria. Integration of TSA into the accounting Education curriculum will make the curriculum responsive to one of the critical provisions of Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) which is the dissemination of knowledge, skills and competencies that contribute to national and local economic goals. It shall, as well, enable Colleges of Education make optimal contribution to national development through intensifying and diversifying its programmes to develop manpower within the needs of the nation, and making professional course contents to reflect the national requirements. Premised on the above submissions, Integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum is a sine qua non for it to reflect the national requirements and equip graduates with skills and competencies to contribute effectively to national development, though not without challenges.

Challenges to Integration of TSA into Accounting Education Curriculum

Integration of Treasury Single Account into the Accounting Education curriculum, though a lofty ambition, may not be attained so easily. Like any other curriculum integration exercise, it is bedevilled by a lot of challenges. The following are the challenges to integration of TSA into Accounting Education Curriculum:

Accounting Education Lecturers Poor Knowledge of TSA:

One of the factors that challenge integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum is Accounting Education lecturers' poor knowledge of TSA. In agreement with Egwu in Okorie (2014), one cannot give the knowledge one does not have. Accounting Education lecturers who were not taught

TSA cannot jump into teaching TSA principles talkless of playing a significant role in making TSA a part of the Accounting Education curriculum. It is a matter of concern that TSA which had a successful test run in 2012 and was fully adopted in 2016 is not yet a part of the Accounting Education programme in Nigeria. Poor knowledge is a very probable cause of this situation and may even make Accounting Education lecturers incapable to initiate or promote integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum.

Poor Funding:

Poor funding is another challenge to the integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. This position is in agreement with that of Duru (2016) which posited that finance is a critical factor that influences curriculum innovation. Reviewing the Accounting Education curriculum to integrate TSA, as a curriculum innovation, would require a reasonable capital outlay. The body that supervises Colleges of Education in the country (the National Commission for Colleges of Education – NCCE) would be involved. Subject experts, professional bodies and other critical stakeholders would also be involved. In the same vein, a lot of other non-human materials would be required. These human and material resources require reasonable amount of money which the country, in the present dispensation, may not easily afford.

Inconsistency in Government Policies:

However, inconsistency in government policies may challenge the integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. Cayton in Engen, Steijn and Tummers (2018) explained that in relation to public policy domain, policy inconsistency can be attributed to the magnitude to which government policies are neither constant nor steady over time. Engen et al (2018) posited that policy inconsistency is attributable to such terms as uncertainty, in

continuity and unpredictability. Be that as it may, TSA is a public policy and may suffer inconsistency in Nigeria as other policies. Successive administrations in Nigeria chart their own courses with no regard to what was in existence before they ascended to power. A swift change from TSA to any other arrangement within a short time is possible. A thoughtless change like that might mess up the idea of integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. The fear of such type of change may discourage relevant stakeholders from the idea of integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum considering what it will take to achieve.

Poor Response to Changes in Economic and Financial Policies:

Another factor is poor response to changes in economic and financial policies by tertiary education supervisory bodies. The National Universities Commission (NUC), National Board for Technical Education (NBTE) and National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) at times, do not review or update Universities, Polytechnics and Colleges of Education Accounting Education curricula on time in response to changes in economic and financial policies. Considering the fact that the gains of the 2012 test run of TSA led to the full adoption of the arrangement by the Federal Republic of Nigeria, one would expect Tertiary Education Institutions in the country to have adopted TSA into the Accounting Education curricula. The 2020 Minimum Standards for Colleges of Education has not taken TSA into account. Decrying the use of obsolete curricula, Bugaje (2023) posited that building infrastructure in higher institutions, especially in the polytechnics, without relevant curricula is equal to keeping a good and beautifully dressed body that has no soul. Bugaje concluded that the use of obsolete curricula to teach must be discontinued. This submission provides clear

evidence that tertiary institutions are not responsive to relevant changes with regard to curricular revision and/or integration. Another evidence of poor curricular response to critical changes in economic and financial policies is of Okorie, Onwe and Unugo (2018) who found that there was low response to International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) by the NCCE and Colleges of Education.

Resistance to Change:

Resistance to change is another challenge to integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. Though change is believed to be constant, most people react negatively to it. Negative reaction to change is what Piderit in Damawan and Azizah (2020) described as resistance to change. Damawan and Azizah agreed that resistance to change can be referred to as individual attitude or behaviour that can frustrate the purpose of change. Bupo (2016) agreed that resistance to change is a barrier to integration of innovation to existing curriculum and reasoned that the resistance itself is not actually the problem but an indication that there is problem somewhere. Inferentially, resistance to change might result from poor motivation, poor funding, and dearth of infrastructure or phobia. However, the underlying truth is that curriculum planners and Accounting Education lecturers are not exempt from resistance to change which is, no doubt, one of the barriers to integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum.

Slavish Attachment to the Existing Curriculum:

Slavish attachment to the existing curriculum is yet another barrier to integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. This attachment works two ways: Accounting Education lecturers may slavishly attachment themselves with excessive and single-minded zeal to the existing curriculum as if adding or dropping would attract divine punishment; again, the supervisory body (precisely,

the NCCE) may overrate the existing curriculum. Under these circumstances, the minimum standards suffice for the Accounting Education lecturer; going outside what is in the minimum standards is inconceivable. This may lead to labouring to cover the given course content or paying eye service to secure accreditation from the supervisory body without giving thought to the achievement of the general aims of education.

Absence of Training for Accounting Education Lecturers:

The fundamental reason for training and retraining of teachers is to update their ability, competences, knowledge and understanding in order to improve their service delivery. Nkomo and Abdi (2023) believed that training is the development of specific attitudes and skills required to perform a given task or series of tasks for optimum productivity and general organizational efficiency. On this premise, the authors of the present study see training of Accounting Education lecturers as continuous assistance or coaching given to make them have current knowledge of the job content and scope, curricular design and implementation, as well as emerging issues in the subject area. The above notwithstanding, some Accounting Education lecturers enter the field without pedagogical training while those with pedagogical training are not given retraining opportunities for continuous professional development. Having no effective pedagogical techniques, lecturers feel comfortable with a faulty, existing curriculum because, according to Biku, Demas, Woldehawariat, Getahun and Mekonnen (2018), the lecturers may not be aware of the issues demanding curricular change, integration, innovation or revision. Similarly, absence of continuing professional development training may create gaps between the expectations on the lecturers with regard to designing effective curriculum, delivering

standard lectures and integrating new economic and financial policies. Absence of training negates the realization of national educational goals and objectives and, impacts negatively on such curricular innovations as integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum of Colleges of Education. However, these challenges have to be overpowered so that Accounting Education programme, at this level, would yield the dividend required of it.

Overcoming the Challenges to Integration of TSA into Accounting Education Curriculum

Nevertheless, the positive side of the matter is that all the factors identified as challenges to the integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum are surmountable; none of them could be described as impossible. Training and re-training of Accounting Education lecturers can act as an elixir to the challenge of little knowledge of TSA on the part of Accounting Education lecturers. Training and re-training agrees with the opinion of Bello, Oludele and Ademiluyi (2016) that held training and re-training of teachers as critical strategies for successful integration of new technologies into the instructional process. Supporting this opinion, Olise and Uliyan (2016) ranked training and re-training of teachers as the first strategy towards the realization of curriculum integration. In the same vein, Umeano and Ifi (2019) ranked in-service-training as the primordial means of achieving success in curriculum integration. Again, in support of this idea, Okoh, Ezzeh and Enwelim (2018) described training and re-training of teachers as a giant stride to effective curriculum integration. Actually, training and re-training helps to update the competence of teachers with regard to contents and methodology. In-service-training, conferences, seminars and workshops will open new channels for Accounting Education lecturers and make them demand for a paradigm

shift. However, poor funding as a challenge to the integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum can be taken care of by ensuring that adequate fund is allocated to Accounting Education programme. TSA should be given a place of priority as an anti-corruption curriculum and then be allowed to attract adequate funding. This agrees with the position of Okoh et al (2018) who opined that giving priority to the funding of an aspect of the curriculum and ensuring that funds allocated are not diverted would enhance the integration of that aspect to the curriculum. These opinions agree with the assertion of Nedum-Ogbede (2016) who opined that allocation of adequate fund by relevant stakeholders would enhance curriculum integration. Adequate funding will facilitate training and re-training of Accounting Education lecturers. In-service-training, conferences, workshops and seminars can only be assessed if there is fund. In the same vein, supervisory bodies require sufficient fund to carry out every curriculum revision exercise. Inconsistency in public policy requires all hands to be on the deck to ensure that it does not forestall integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. Those in power should act in obedience to policy directions and make credible policies in accordance with appropriate guidelines. Policies shall not be based on the whims and caprices of those in power nor made with the intention to provide leverage to the privileged. The academic community should not stand aloof and watch politicians change policies as the change clothes; academics should invite those in power to symposia, conferences, seminars, fora and workshops for the purpose of guiding them aright. In the same vein, professional bodies like Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN), Institute of Certified Public Accountants of Nigeria (ICPAN) and Chartered Institute of Public

Administrators (CIPAN) should, as well, interact with those in power with regard to public policy consistency. Poor response to critical changes in economic and financial policies on the part of curriculum planners can be mitigated by stabilizing inconsistency in public policies. Curriculum planners would be much more eager to respond to economic and financial policies if they are assured of relative consistency of public policies. In the same vein, involving curriculum planners in making policies that affect them will make curriculum planners/implementers give rapid response to the policies. Both curriculum planners and implementers get committed if they are involved in policy making and this, in turn, makes them respond faster to the provisions of the policy (Odim, 2021). This position agrees with the position of Olorunleke (2018) who opined that teachers are the most qualified resource persons to be consulted in taking decisions that involve education. When teachers (Accounting Education lecturers) are made stakeholders in policy making and are properly motivated, they would put in their best and even agitate for reflection of the policy in the curriculum. Again, teachers who were not involved in making changes that are relevant in their fields of study could be committed to the implementation of the changes through re-training programmes like seminars, conferences and workshops. However, re-training programmes like symposia, conferences, seminars and workshops can help solve the problem of resistance to change. These programmes are expected to prepare the mind of curriculum planners/implementers for the change that might result from integration of TSA into the Accounting Education curriculum. Re-training will douse or handle two of the major reasons for resistance to change: the information which the proposer of the change has, will be made available to the operators; while the skills and abilities those

resisting the change feared that they may not be able to develop will also be made available (Primeast, 2020). Re-training programmes will, as well, provide Accounting Education lecturers with the communication and education required to judge in favour of the change. In the same manner, the participation involved therein reduces resistance to change. Membership to professional bodies like ICAN, ANAN and ICPAN will widen the horizon of Accounting Education lecturers and liberate them from slavish attachment to existing curricula. In the same vein, mandatory professional development programmes like conferences, workshops, seminars and symposia will enable Accounting Education lecturers to come out from their shells and even begin to design the curriculum to suit time and environment. Mandatory professional development programmes will build Accounting Education lecturers to stand on their feet and apply the major principle of situated cognition theory which, according to Cummins (2020), postulates that learning and the context of its acquisition are inseparable. They will begin to approach accounting curriculum holistically based on economic and financial realities. Once exposed Accounting Education lecturers adopt TSA, diffusion of innovation theory which LaMorte (2019) described as a valuable change model will take over, through communication and peer-to-peer networking, the change will spread until it becomes an aspect of the curriculum.

Conclusion

Treasury Single Account (TSA) is an anti-corruption arrangement that should be integrated into the Accounting Education curriculum especially in a public-sector-driven economy like Nigeria. Integration of TSA into the curriculum is challenged by such factors as poor funding, inconsistency in government policies, resistance to change and

slavish attachment to existing curriculum. These challenges could be handled through training and re-training of Accounting Education lecturers, adequate funding and operation of a flexible curriculum.

Recommendation

The researchers made the following recommendations:

1. Accounting Education lecturers should have a strong association that would be organizing mandatory annual professional development programmes for members.
2. Government and other proprietors of Colleges of Education should provide adequate fund for Accounting Education programme.
3. Accounting Education programmes should adopt flexible curricula so that Accounting Education lecturers can informally integrate innovations in economic and financial policies.
4. Accounting Education lecturers should be encouraged to join chartered accounting professional bodies like ICAN, ANAN, and ICPAN to cater for their professional development.
5. Government should involve Accounting Education lecturers in formulation of economic and financial policies that concern Accounting Education.

References

- Arinze, F. O., & Chukwuka, J. N. (2018). Curriculum innovation models and implementation strategies: Implications for social studies teachers. In I. N. Nwankwo, E. A. Nwachukwu, A. I. Ibeh, V. E. Okafor, & J. O. C. Okekeokosisi (Eds.), *Education and national development: Issues and way forward* (pp. xx-xx). Ikwo: Ebonyi State College of Education Ikwo Printing Press.
- Awojiokinor, E. M., & Binta, M. Y. (2022). Integrating anti-corruption education in Nigeria: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Educational Studies, Trends & Practice*, 230, 230–237.
- Bello, G. A., Oludele, L. Y., & Ademiluyi, A. B. (2016). Impact of information and communication technology on teaching and learning. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 3(1), 189–197.
- Biku, T., Demas, T., Woldehawariat, N., Getahun, M., & Mekonnen, A. (2018). The effect of teaching without pedagogical training in St. Paul's Hospital, Millennium Medical College, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. *Advances in Medical Education and Practice*, 9, 893–904.
- Bugaje, I. (2023, February 2). Nigerian schools using 30 years old curriculum, NBTE laments. *The Guardian*.
- Bupo, G. O. (2016). Effects of technology on secretarial education students' performance in software application. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 3(1), 369–377.
- Central Bank of Nigeria. (2016). Guidelines for the operation of treasury single account (TSA) by state governments of Nigeria: A white paper issued by the CBN in February.
- Cummins, E. (2020, May 4). Situated cognition: Theory & definition. Retrieved from <https://study.com>
- Damawan, A. H., & Azizah, S. (2020). Resistance to change: Causes and strategies as an organizational challenge. *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research* 395 49–53.

- Duru, V. N. (2016). Curriculum studies: Concepts, development and implementation. *Owerri: Avann Global Publications*.
- Eneja, R. U., & Akamigbo, I. S. (2020). Evaluation of accounting education programme in colleges of education in South East Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice, 11(8)*, 39–45.
- Engen, N. V., Steijin, B., & Tummers, L. (2018). Do consistent government policies lead to greater meaningfulness and legitimacy on the front line? *Public Administration, 97(1)*, 97–115.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria. (2013). National policy on education (6th ed.). Lagos: *Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council*.
- LaMorte, W. W. (2019). Diffusion of innovation theory. Retrieved May 5, 2020, from sphweb.bumc.edu
- Maali, B., & Al-Attar, A. M. (2020). Accounting curricula in universities and market needs: The Jordan case. *SAGE Journals*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244019899463>
- Mba, I. (2016). Treasury single account (in Nigeria): Issues and implications. A paper presented at Covenant University, Canaan land Ota, Nigeria.
- Nedum-Ogbede, P. O. (2016). New technologies in business education: Challenges and the way forward. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education, 3(2)*, 104–111.
- Nkomo, N., & Abdi, U. M. (2023). Impacts of training and retraining of teachers in primary and post-primary schools for better performance. *Journal of Educational Research, 14(3)*, 1–6.
- Obih, S. O. A. (2018). Selecting economics curriculum content. In I. N. Nwankwo, E. A. Nwachukwu, A. I. Ibeh, V. E. Okafor, & J. O. C. Okeke okosisi (Eds.), *Education and national development: Issues and way forward (pp. xx-xx)*. Ikwo: *Ebonyi State College of Education Ikwo Printing Press*.
- Ocheni, S. (2016, January 25). Treasury single account: A catalyst for public financial management in Nigeria. *The Nation Newspaper*.
- Odewole, P. O. (2016). Treasury single account: A tool for effective cash management in Nigeria. *Journal of Finance and Accounting, 4(6)*, 328–335.
- Odim, O. O. (2021). Curriculum planning and implementation. In C. P. Akpan, E. S. Uko, & R. O. Oshim (Eds.), *Educational planning in Nigeria: Principles and practices (pp. xx-xx)*. Calabar, Nigeria: *University of Calabar Press*.
- Offorma, G. C. (2016). Integrating components of culture in curriculum planning. *International Journal of Curriculum and Instruction, 8(1)*, 1–8.
- Okoh, K. C., Ezzeh, P. O., & Enwelim, J. O. (2018). Impact of ICT/digitally literate education and national development: Issues and way forward. In I. N. Nwankwo, E. A.

- Nwachukwu, A. I. Ibeh, V. E. Okafor, & J. O. C. Okekeokosisi (Eds.), *Education and national development: Issues and way forward* (pp. xx-xx). Ikwo: Ebonyi State College of Education Ikwo Printing Press.
- Okorie, O. (2014). Perceived adequacy of human and material resources required for effective implementation of upper basic education business studies curriculum in Ebonyi State (Unpublished M.Ed. dissertation). Department of Business Education, Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki.
- Okorie, O., Onwe, O. U., &Unugo, L. (2018). International financial reporting standards (IFRS) education in colleges of education in Southeastern States of Nigeria. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 6(11), 1460–1464.
- Olise, J., &Ulisan, E. (2016). Functional approaches to ICT courses in business education: A recipe for producing efficient graduates. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 3(1), 225–236.
- Olorunleke, I. A. (2018). Problems and prospects of curriculum planning and implementation in the Nigerian educational system. *Journal of Teacher Perspective*, 8(2), 1–10.
- Primeast. (2020, August 19). 7 strategies for overcoming resistance to change in the workplace. Retrieved from primeast.com
- Rashed, Z. N., &Tamuri, A. H. (2020). Integrated curriculum model in Islamic education curriculum. *International Journal of Academic Research*, 12(7), 214–223.
- Udo, B. (2016, March 17). 15 things to know about treasury single account (TSA). *Premium Times*.
- Udo, E. J., & Esara, I. E. (2016). Adoption of treasury single account (TSA) by state governments of Nigeria: Benefits, challenges, and prospects. *Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 4(3), 126–130.
- Umeano, N. E., &Ifi, C. C. (2019). Extent of integration challenges of new technologies in teaching business education courses in tertiary institutions. *Nigerian Journal of Business Education*, 6(1), 235–245.
- Wall, A., & Leckie, A. (2017). Curriculum integration: An overview. *Current Issues in Middle Level Education*, 22(1), 36–40.